

The role of Counseling in the labyrinth of modern era¹

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In a world in frenzy, where everything changes so rapidly and on daily basis, it is impossible to predict or even suspect the way the future will look like. In an environment like this, what role would Counseling play and in what way Counseling should adjust and keep being supportive, productive and successful as a service for people in need?

Key words: Counseling, individual, crisis, training, life skills

Predicting the...past?

Even though the title seems a bit strange, if we think about it we find that today any prediction about the future is an attempt to predict the past. Let's just consider that the world around us is changing at a pace so terrifying and stunning that it is almost impossible to predict how it will look like in a year or two. That wasn't very difficult to do in the past, as reality was changing in a much slower pace.

People are trying to predict the future from the moment they realize the terms *identity* and *existence*: next day, next month, next year, next decade etc. this is our nature, obviously. The point is that the technological labyrinth in which we live today, how accurate our predictions can be or are predictions even possible? Our systems and techniques, developed over the years, are still practical and useful? Until now, we wanted to predict as many aspects of human life as possible, taking into account as many parameters as possible, based on our data collection, on processing and classification in such a way that we could get the feeling of projecting ourselves into the future and make it visible: economy, market, sciences, and everyday situations. In other words, the feeling of stability and control over our lives.

The world today, however, has features that can easily destabilize everything easily and instantly and the economic crisis that began in 2007, has changed once and for all the world, proving that these parameters truly exist. And there are more: international terrorism, technology galloping, collapsing of values, democracy, institutions and any stable system we thought we had.

Of course we live in this world long before this situation, long enough to know that these destabilizing factors existed long before the great economic crisis of the great awakening. But

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sometimes, certain constants prevent us from realizing how deep this crisis is. Constants that have now collapsed and were part of our identity and the tissue that held together the inner structure we perceive as *self*. But what happens to the identity of the individual, the *self*, when situations are pushing and they are changing and the social frame is falling apart?

The identity is linked to the various levels of social structures: interpersonal relationships, groups, systems and social organizing (Abrams & Vasiljevic, 2013). Beyond the given identity, which is unavoidable, such as gender or race lies the elective identity (-ies) such as political beliefs and beyond the elective lies the unwanted identity (-ies) such as unemployment.

According to the relevant psychological theories, the formation of identity is based on three elements: the core of the personality and the interactions and social structures in which those interactions occur (Cote & Levine, 2002). People adopt roles and within these roles they recognize each other and develop expectations based on the identity which creates these roles. Individuals therefore, define themselves not only according to the inner core of their personality, but also, and perhaps to a greater extent, by the reflection of the other and the interactions with others, along with their expectations (Burke & Stets, 2009).

The mixture of these elements becomes an edifice which is perceived as *self* and which the individual begins to take for granted, without being aware that many events can have a serious impact on it, diminish or alter it quite easily (Virgo, 2001). The current crisis, the depth and duration of it, especially with so many crises in the crisis, is frightening and powerful enough to change a person's environment and identity (Wee, 2014).

The major crises of the past have been overcome and the recovery usually began after a few years, but the current crisis is already approaching a decade in duration and no one can predict how long will last or for how long we will still feel the vibrations after the recovery point. Today, it is crucial for the individual to adopt roles which not only he does not want and haven't chose, but roles that he/she is afraid of too. The individual must live in an uncertain world, where the elements of security and stability of the past, no longer exist. With no compass and no guidance he must preserve his identity alone, something unimaginably difficult (Cote & Levine, 2009).

Which is the role of Counseling is such a reality? How can Counsellors work more productive and more efficiently in a complicated and hostile environment? To answer these questions we must first determine the previous role of Counseling, a role which is crucial beyond doubt. Counseling, both vocational and psychological seek to provide information, support and guidance to the client, trying to anticipate and map the future. It is important to understand that until now the system is mostly supporting and not training, in the sense that the services provided relate more to the support of the individual in making decisions on his future, something that apparently is now harder or even impossible, under the new circumstances.

Furthermore, there two more challenges for the counsellor: a large part of the middle class in now in need for support and the crisis strike the counsellor himself, both professionally and personally. Leaving aside –for the moment- the increasing workload and focusing on the impact on the counsellor, a question arises inevitably: if the counsellor is in the same or similar situation as the client, how can he/she provide sufficient and quality services? The answer, however, is simple. In

fact the counsellor is not in the same position, as he/she is a trained and qualified person, capable of dealing with problems and challenges. We are talking about persons with life skills.

There's no need analyzing further the matter, therefore let's focus on the matter of training and the importance of learning how to deal with the challenges and problems on a personal and professional level. For it is obvious that in a context where predictions and guidelines are no longer easy, only the inner arsenal can bring the desired results and these are the preservation and management of life. Third party supporting programs and customized plans alone, may not be the solution in this brave and unpredictable new world. Then what is?

Maybe we should start making fewer predictions and try more to train individuals and groups in life skills that will empower them in order to navigate in the chaos (and not outside the chaos) by themselves. The world is now too fluid to be controlled but it is possible to flow in it and with it. Each individual must learn to adapt quickly, taking and creating opportunities and where there are no chances for opportunities, be patience and focused.

The chaos as a labyrinth: inside, outside or making circles?

If the world is a labyrinth –which it is- then the one who is standing outside this labyrinth –which is impossible- is essentially unrealistic. People are made of labyrinths: our mind, our body, our free will, our relationships. But the world today is not a simple labyrinth, it's a rather complicated one, a labyrinth that's constantly changing its shape, its size and design and there's nobody who can draw an image that keeps changing, transforming into something different every time. You can give it a shot, but it will lead you nowhere or somewhere near there.

But what we learn from the myth of Theseus and the Minotaur in the labyrinth? Actually, a lot! First of all, that the labyrinth have monsters. Then –and this is the crucial information- that Theseus was worrying more about the labyrinth than the Minotaur. Why? Because he knew his strength and he knew what was beyond his powers. He was prepared for the Minotaur, but not for the labyrinth. He had no doubt that while inside he will encounter the monster and he had no doubt that he could beat it, but he also had no doubt that his biggest problem was the labyrinth, therefore he needed some extra help: the thread of Ariadne. The confidence and security to take action. His compass in the labyrinth.

I believe that counsellors today are invited to play a similar role. Not so much to think how they beat the monster, but rather how to strengthen and train the individual, in order to navigate in the labyrinth of the new reality. Marcel Proust once wrote that the true journey is not about new places, but having new eyes. This is counsellor's new call: to provide new eyes. To teach skills and the use of those skills and how to walk in the labyrinth after beating the monster. The thread of Ariadne might be the training in life skills in a way that the individual will be able to find a way (as many times as necessary) to move forward.

We live in extremely complicated times, where the borderlines between the frames of life are not as clear as they used to be, whether we talk about age, profession, social life or any other role or identity. The prolonged economic crisis has already crashed any sense of security and certainty

associated with the identity and in the empty spaces are now evolving new unpleasant and unwanted characteristics, such as stress, insecurity and psychological pressure. Now, people are treated as numbers and costs to be reduced and this way of thinking has blocked any substantial investment in people and social services, with the consequences we already know.

In order to understand the uniqueness of the situation today, consider the relationship between the condition of unemployment and work. A few years ago it was very easy to see the separating lines between the two conditions. But can you see them clearly today? The individual that have a job, is facing complications and problems of similar or the same nature as the individual that is jobless and in such extent that counselling must come up with a new plan and a new supporting framework for lifelong guidance.

The majority of the people that do have a job are now under great and increasing pressure for better performance and higher productivity, with minimum support and fewer resources, with no motives and their income increased to the minimum. The result is to engage in struggling performances in order to survive in an unsupportive working environment that doesn't please them, with varying emotional and physical challenges and dilemmas, intense working stress and huge gaps between work, family and personal life and a constant fear of losing that job, despite the low wages and the lack of motivation. Therefore, unemployed, working people, young, middle-aged and elderly people are in a greater need for support, guidance and motivation (Stavrou, 2015). It is remarkable that the former basic unemployed management strategies, such as psychological support, education, self-control and self-esteem development are now necessary to everybody, regardless personal and/or social status.

Until now, counselling was trying to examine, determine and finally predict and plan the future, depending on the skills and the ability and the insight of the counsellor rather than the individual of interest. This doesn't mean that it was wrong as a practice, but it is unlikely to work well today and under the new ever-changing needs.

Assuming that everything is well as regards our services, after a while, a new change or a new destabilizing factor cancels the plan made not so long ago. The labyrinth is changed its form and shape again and the *predicted* future comes with a new face. A new face that won't last long.

The new contract of Counselling

Within this labyrinth, it is crucial to bring Motivation Counselling, Psychology and Career Counselling together, in order to provide guidance and information along with training. It is a fact that today people find it difficult to cope, even with the simplest things, let alone indulge in any plans for the future, therefore it is very important for everyone to learn and be able to use specific skills and techniques.

In a world that is so uncertain, Spinelli urges us to abandon the burden of security and embrace uncertainty. It's the only way to become active on the social scene and personal life. Only if the individual learns how to live in uncertainty can be creative and survive. Just think that even if this

crisis end tomorrow, its impact will hold on for years to come and of course the world will never be the same.

Therefore, the greatest art is to seek and find the resources outside yourself, unchanged through time and then use them to navigate in a fluid world. This art of being is the only certainty that remained intact and strong and the role of the counsellor is to provide these resources and teach these skills to the individuals in need, in order for everyone to become stronger, more efficient and more rational.

Counselling is invited to keep up the good work of the past, but also to create and provide positive expectations and positive feeling that will rise above the sea of denial. Therefore, we must keep providing support, but now we must also provide education and training and teach techniques that will change the perception of life, give hope and desire to overcome the obstacles. In another level, groups at risk, experiencing uncertain situations (isolation, social exclusion etc.) need to be protected and supported too.

It is a fact that this task is not easy. But changes don't come easy, anyway. Counselling had always had to adopt to situations and provide good services no matter difficult it was. A good start would be the inclusion of counselling in other projects and training programs, even if they are not strictly relevant to social services and in that way more and more individuals will take part and enjoy the benefits of life skill training. These individuals can then support and help their families and friends in the same way.

Moreover, specific counselling and basic life skills plans can be designed, based on the keys of identity development, communication and problem solving skills and provide them in schools, pre-service training, open universities and conferences, media etc. Of course life skills are not something new, but we haven't –as yet- managed to intergrade training in education plans. Furthermore, it is essential to re-adjust career counselling in order to cover pre-profession, inter-profession and post-profession periods of life, not in theory but in practice and as a resource and support mechanism. In the new world that's unfolding before us careers must now be approached as a skill, not as an achievement.

Instead of an epilogue: The importance of training – a metaphor

My young son discovered his hands and feet.
When it was time for riding his first bike
I had to show him how to use his feet.
When he had to face a flat tire
I had to show him how to use his hands.
Now, if he can't ride it and he can't fix it
He can carry it home,
Because now he knows
How to use his feet
And how to use his hands.

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